

Between Risk and Hope: Demographic Change and (Return)Migration in Latvia Amid Russia's War in Ukraine

Version 1

Description

Project "Between Risk and Hope: Demographic Change and (Return)Migration in Latvia Amid Russia's War in Ukraine (Nr. VPP-IZM-Letonika-2025/1-0002)".

The project explores demography, migration, and return migration within the context of current geopolitical, socio-economic, and regional changes in Latvia. It considers Russia's war in Ukraine as a structural shock that alters how people in Latvia and its diaspora make decisions about family formation, emigration, return, and integration. Drawing on theories of risk society, ontological security, and hope/future imaginaries, it examines how perceived insecurity and future expectations influence demographic behaviour. The project consists of five substantive work packages: 1) civic "X-Day" imaginaries and their demographic implications; 2) fertility and family strategies amidst insecurity; 3) return migration potential in the Latvian UK diaspora; 4) media discourse on migration; 5) integration experiences of post-2022 Ukrainian refugees, along with recent Belarusian and Russian migrants. Using mixed methods, including a nationally representative survey, survey and conjoint experiments, participant observation, and in-depth interviews, the project will produce reusable datasets, academic publications, policy briefs, regional outreach events, and a book. By working with Latvia's ministries responsible for demography, welfare, defence, diaspora, and integration, it will provide evidence-based recommendations to improve population resilience, return migration strategies, and demographic policy planning amid long-term geopolitical pressures.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS VPP-IZM-Letonika-2025/1-0002

Grant

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University, University of Latvia, Rigas Ekonomikas augstskola "Stockholm School of Economics in Riga"

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Between Risk and Hope: Demographic Change and \(Return\)Migration in Latvia Amid Russia's War in Ukraine](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: VPP-IZM-Letonika-2025/1-0002

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Between Risk and Hope: Demographic Change and
(Return)Migration in Latvia Amid Russia's War in Ukraine

Template: RSU DMP Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Implementation of the project and production of the outputs, especially the publications and conference entries.

For these ends, we will conduct a nationally representative poll with approximately 50-100 closed questions, including survey experiments (n = 1000-2000). We will conduct two narrower polls - one among Latvian youth on demographic issues (n = 500-1000) and another among Ukrainian refugees in Latvia (n = 300-400). We will also conduct in-depth, semi-structured interviews with Ukrainian refugees and Belarusian and Russian migrants (n = 45-50). We will organize future self-interviews with members of the Latvian diaspora in the United Kingdom. We will also conduct web scraping to analyze migration-related sentiment in traditional media and social media in Latvia. Other methods will include participant observation, ethnographic research, conceptual and normative analysis, and focus groups.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Other researchers and policy makers.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Experimental data
- Textual data
- Coded textual data
- Observation data
- Ratings

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- SAV
- XLS

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

20 MB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

Only data that has not been previously generated is set to be generated. A literature review and data exploration were conducted beforehand to avoid data duplication. Furthermore, we are interested in data from 2026 through 2028, which is not yet available.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook
- ReadMe file

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

PDF files can be opened with standard PDF readers, such as Adobe Acrobat Reader, or in web browsers. CSV and XLS/XLSX files can be opened and managed using spreadsheet software such as Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets, or LibreOffice Calc. SAV files can be accessed primarily using IBM SPSS Statistics, with compatibility for analysis in statistical software such as R or Python when needed.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access to the data is restricted. Requests for access may be submitted to the authors, accompanied by a proposal for collaboration.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2028-12-21

Indefinitely

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Security
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU covers majority of costs including storage and long term preservation. RSU ensures the IT infrastructure for storage, archiving, re-use, security, long-term preservation. RSU Dataverse will be used for long term preservation.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

Riga Stradiņš University

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

Māris Andžāns (orcid: [0000-0002-4695-3929](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4695-3929))

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Mārtiņš Kaprāns (orcid: [0000-0003-4938-1601](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4938-1601))
- Jānis Juzefovičs (orcid: [0000-0001-7285-1806](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7285-1806))
- Zane Varpina (0000-0003-2707-6040)
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- Klāvs Sedlenieks (orcid: [0000-0002-1751-2956](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1751-2956))

Comment:

The five leaders of the working packages will involve their subordinates when they are hired. Some of the data will be gathered by outsourced companies, but in cooperation and supervision of the project employees.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data will be reviewed during the preparation and summarization phases by the working packages leaders and their subordinates

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Physical access control
- Other

No personal or otherwise sensitive data will be stored long term. The data obtained will be pseudonymized or anonymized at earliest possibility.

The research data obtained within the project will be stored in an institutionally managed secure cloud environment (such as the RSU Nextcloud system), which

complies with European Union data protection requirements and institutional information security policies.

To ensure data security, the following measures will be implemented:

Access to the data will be granted only to authorized project personnel, based on user roles and the “need-to-know” principle;

Each user will be provided with an individual user account;

Access to the data will be protected by passwords with defined validity periods and two-factor authentication (2FA);

Data will be protected through encryption, firewalls, and institutional security monitoring mechanisms;

Access rights to files and folders will be regularly reviewed and adjusted in accordance with evolving data processing needs throughout the project.

Personal data and other sensitive information will be anonymized at the earliest possible stage of the research.

Researchers without access to institutional devices will follow all rules as closely as possible.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing
- Other

No personal or otherwise sensitive data will be stored. All data will be anonymized

Data security will be ensured by providing for:

- * clearly defined responsibility for data processing and access rights management, entrusted to the project's data controller;
- * regular review of access rights, particularly in cases where researchers' roles or stages of data processing change;
- * data processing in accordance with institutional data protection policies and applicable legal regulations (see the Research Data Management Policy, e.g., the Nextcloud terms of use);
- * anonymization or pseudonymization of personal data at the earliest possible stage of the research;
- * storage of informed consent forms and other identifying documents separately from the research data;
- * informing project staff about data security requirements and principles of good practice (e.g., close cooperation with data curators and participation in relevant training activities).

These measures ensure that data are processed securely throughout their entire lifecycle – from collection to long-term storage and publication in anonymized form.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

During the study, all project data will be stored in an institutionally managed secure cloud environment (e.g., the RSU-maintained Nextcloud system), which ensures controlled access, data protection, and compliance with European Union data protection requirements.

Sensitive and non-anonymized data (e.g., interview recordings or transcripts prior to anonymization) will be stored exclusively within this secure institutional environment. Anonymized data may be used for analysis and collaboration within the project, while remaining stored in the same institutional environment.

Researchers' personal devices will be used solely as workstations to access the institutional data storage environment. Long-term storage of data on personal devices is not planned.

Data will be stored in this environment throughout the entire duration of the project. After the completion of the project, anonymized research data will be transferred to the RSU Dataverse repository for long-term preservation and reuse in accordance with the project's data availability conditions.

Researchers without access to institutional devices will follow these rules as closely as possible.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

Working versions of the data used during the study (e.g., non-anonymized interview recordings or transcripts) will be stored only for as long as necessary for data processing and anonymization.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long-term preservation and curation

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored?
Who will have access to these documents?

Forms will not be stored electronically. They will be stored by the working party leaders in their offices' locked drawers with controlled access only to the necessary personnel until the end of the project and subsequently shredded.

In ethnographic research, particularly where questions involve sensitive subjects or topics, oral consent will be obtained from participants rather than written consent; such consent will neither be recorded nor documented with a signature.

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.7 Is the collected/generated data intended to be processed outside the EU?

Yes. UK. Consulting will be done with Marina Siņkovska, DPS.

3.3.8 Is the collected/generated personal data intended to be used for profiling and/or automated decision-making?

No

3.3.9 Is artificial intelligence intended to be used in the processing of collected/generated sensitive or personal data?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- Privacy policies
- National laws

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